

ENHANCING THE SUITABILITY OF HIGH VALUED COST ITEMS IN E-COMMERCE

¹Akazue M. I., ²Ekurume E. O., & ³Efozia F. N.

^{1,2}Delta State University, Abraka, Nigeria

³Prototype Engineering Development Institute (PEDI), NASENI, Federal Ministry of Science & Technology, Ilesha, Osun state

Corresponding Author: ²elohorogaga@gmail.com, 08147809321

ABSTRACT

High value cost items like jewelries, gold, silver, diamond and other precious ornaments receive the red flag from buyers on the electronic commerce platform. The red flag is due to the cost and value of the items, lack of trust and the lack of facility to inspect, verify and/or authenticate the item before purchase is made. Due to these factors, such high valued items find little or no presence in the electronic commerce market. This research paper proposes a novel approach towards boosting consumer confidence in high valued cost items in electronic commerce business platform through online verification and inspection. Also, the paper shows how the suitability of high valued cost items in e-commerce business platform is enhanced through the application of image processing technologies embedded into electronic commerce systems. In this proposed model, customers are given the opportunity to upload a live image from their home and compare it with the image of the item they intend to purchase. The higher the percentage of similarity in the comparison shows the authenticity of the online item and vice-versa. This comparison is also performed by merchant system on all proposed items from prospective sellers as well. The equivalence of image is solely based on manufacturers embedded trademark, which are extracted through image edge detection and pixel wise comparison.

Keywords: *E-Commerce, B2C e-commerce, Embedded software, High Valued Cost Items, Image processing*

1.0 Introduction

The traditional commerce is simply the buying and selling of products and it has been around since the beginning of time while Electronic commerce also known as e-commerce began when the internet was first introduced for commercial purposes. E-commerce, defined by many literatures, narrow down to business transactions that are carried out with the aid of information technologies, such as computer, internet, etc, along with other technologies like Electronic Data interchange [EDI] for information exchange and Electronic fund transfer [EFT] for fund between the users of the e-commerce platform . The introduction of electronic commerce has totally changed the global business and economic advancement, due to its borderless and seamless accessibility of all business transactions, hence breaking the bondage of time and location experienced in traditional commerce (Mahadevan, 2000). This success is influenced by the type of goods a company is dealing on and this type of goods is a factor to successful operation and

suitability of a business model for electronic commerce (Dittmann et al, 2002, Ahmad & Sultan (2013)).

Business suitability in electronic commerce such as online ticketing and shipment tracking, online order for audio and video, and online order for books and domestic electronics is well fitted as there are no requirements for inspections. Consumers' confidence is boosted by the trust worthiness of the merchants, which in turn ensures that only credible sellers are registered on their systems (Hayes and Finnegan, 2003). Also, Johar et al., (2011) insisted that an organization progress in commerce cannot completely be electronic but in addition to traditional models. For example, high valued cost items such as gold, silver jewelries and other precious ornaments, that require inspection before purchase, are always purchased onsite by customers. Presently, the sales of items such as gold silver, diamond, jewelries and other precious ornaments has little or no presence in e-commerce platform (Abdullah and Robert, 2012) .

Globally, millions of businesses exist but very few are fully adapted to electronic commerce business transactions due to the level of customers trust, retailers trust and merchants' stability (Kwok et al., 2000). Table1 is a survey that is limited to few businesses and their suitability for e-commerce, traditional commerce, and a combination of e-commerce and traditional commerce

Table 1: Businesses and their Suitability for E-commerce, Traditional commerce, plus a combination of e-commerce and traditional commerce

	E-COMMERCE	E-COMMERCE & TRADITIONAL COMMERCE	TRADITIONAL COMMERCE ONLY
1	Online Books Order	Roommate Matching	Impulse Items
2	Online Videos Order	Car	Small Quantity Order
3	Online Cloths /Shoes Order	Real Estate	Vegetables And Groceries
4	Online Shipment Tracking	Gold	
5	Online Personal Electronics Gadgets Order	Silver	
6		Jewelries	

2.0 Related Works

2.1 Image processing and e-commerce

Despite the huge success that e-commerce has enjoyed over the years, high valued cost items are yet to fit properly in the e-business transactions. In electronic commerce, several programming languages provide support for this technology, such as java, c# and Dot-Net. These tools are same for development of image processing system (Kwok et al., 2000). Due to the similarity in development technologies for both e-commerce systems and image processing, e-commerce systems uses embedded multimedia, animated and static images to describe items. Image processing is the manipulation of digital images to explore its invisible properties (Zhao, 1997;

Johar et al., 2011). Hence, image processing application in electronic commerce is highly important in enhancing the suitability of high valued cost items in e-commerce transaction. This is achieved through the use of real time image analysis that determines the equality and accuracy of images. This approach authenticates high valued items from sellers and verifies same items to prospective buyers.

In transaction security, numerous authors have employed stenographical cytological techniques for electronic commerce security. Qingjie et al., (2015) introduced the use of water mark in electronic commerce security, specifically focusing on monoecism. Furthermore, image processing in electronic commerce has been used by Kumar et al., (2002) to examine the biometric image processing in electronic commerce security. Sherekar et al., (2008) and Kwok et al., (2004) examines intellectual property right protection in electronic commerce and electronic government application using image water mark technique. Their studies revealed multiple alternatives for developers to select water mark appropriately for intellectual property right protection in election commerce and government application. Kwok et al., (2004) presented how watermark can be used for high user acceptance and how information can be transmitted and controlled by the user. These watermark design pattern was used for protection of intellectual property right in online content distribution electronic commerce application for four major media data (video, audio, image and text). The result of their study showed an enhancement of the choice of digital watermarking to be used in electronic commerce application by developers. Zhao (1997) proposed a low cost and efficient solution that applies watermark image processing technology to electronic commerce.

Also, product accessibility and search engine aspect of electronic commerce has focused on enhancing customer's accessibility of e-commerce product by employing image processing to ensure customers satisfaction. Zhou et al., (2007) examined the use of image-based search engine for improving e-commerce transaction, especially satisfying customers through easy access to products on the mobile e-commerce. Furthermore, North (2014) emphasized the use of quality images in electronic commerce for product catalogue as a way of improving customers' satisfaction and accessibility to product with the overall goal of creating a better shopping experience that increases customer trust. Also, North (2014) clearly stated the importance of image processing. Shamoil et al., (2015) proposed a fuzzy color image retrieval technique for e-commerce as a replacement for conventional image tagging retrieval method in ecommerce.

Image originality is very important for e-commerce (Sharma and Abrol, 2013). Image authentication is another aspect of image processing and electronic commerce emphasis has been on the authenticity of product images as a way of preventing false product image description. This is due to the ease of image alteration, as a result of the availability of sophisticated tools for image processing, hence making it a challenge (Sharma and Abrol, 2013). Also, the research by Sharma and Abrol (2013) presented an overview of image authentication importance in numerous areas including e-commerce security and emphasis was on the need for authentication of image. Therefore the use of image processing in electronic commerce spans a lot of area,

amongst which this research paper is considering, enhancing the suitability of high valued cost items to boost customer's trust and sellers return on investment anticipation.

3.0 Proposed design of high valued cost items business models

Schneider (2005), in introduction to electronic commerce, described high valued items as items which are very expensive, with high financial value and involvements. Examples of such items are gold, silver, jewelry, diamond and other precious stones/ornaments. Due to the fact that these items are known as high capital intensive ventures, sellers and buyers are skeptical of fraudulent activities. On the consumer side, they are careful to avoid buying items less the value of their money. While on the sellers side, they are at risk of low return on investment, which is a critical point considered before venturing into any business investment. Unfortunately, determining this in electronic commerce is practically impossible but theoretically possible.

The architecture valued cost items business adaptability on electronic commerce model in Figure 1 is broken into three levels; which are

- i. The customer item authentication level
- ii. The seller authentication level
- iii. Merchant authentication level

Figure 1: The Architecture valued cost items business adaptability on electronic commerce model

LEVEL 1- Customer authentication: A registered prospective buyer search for items at this level, then takes a snap shot of similar item to compare with the image of the item advertised on the merchant site. The authentication of item is done at level 3 using edge detection and pixel wise comparison to ascertain the authenticity of items based on manufacturer's trade embedded trademarks. It is a collection of items advertised images and a web based image processor. Depending on the percentage of equivalence returned, the user confidence is boosted, and encouraged to buy item, after this proxy verification and inspection.

LEVEL 2 -Sellers authentication: each registered seller of a highly valued item uploads details of their item to the allocated shop online. This item details, including description, is matched with already existing uploaded similar item information in the database in level 3 using edge detection and pixel wise comparison. Once verified, depending on the percentage of equivalent that is returned by the system, the seller's item is accepted for onward advertisement to prospective customers.

LEVEL 3 Item authentication: Merchants authentication is an independent third party that ensure all set standards are met for prospective sellers to upload their products to the system and also prospective buyers requirements as regards genuinely is satisfied through electronic inspection and verification, without the need for users to go physically to shops in order to acquire these high valued cost items. The level 3 is concerned with verifying the authenticity of the items displayed by sellers on the merchant system, using image comparism processing between already stored item images on merchant system with those uploaded by sellers during the registration of their items. Also, the level 3 handles proxy inspection and verification for prospective buyers or customers by using image processing to compare and return percentage of buyers own image of similar item uploaded or snapped in real-time with those of the same item stored in the merchant items repository. Hence Figure 2 classifies the services of level 3 into two, as follows;

- i. Merchant item authentication
- ii. Customer item authentication

Figure 2: Classifying the Services of Level 3 Item Authentication

Merchant item authentication: is based on the use of merchant item image database for matching equality and resemblance of image of items provided by sellers on the merchant system, in a pixel by pixel matching. It is an alternative item authentication provided to users who do not have sample image or photo of the item they intend to verify and eventually buy.

Customer item authentication is also image comparison between images of items displayed by sellers and image of similar items owned by the prospective buyer. When there are more similar pixels, it means that there is more likelihood of the item authenticity. Also, when the image pixel comparison equality is less, it means that the item authenticity will be less.

3.1 Model execution flow chart

The execution flow is divided into two as shown in figure 3. The first being customers/buyers authentication, where all registered prospective customers enter to visit the online shop, browse highly valued and costly item catalogues, selects their desired items and upload image of similar item they already have, that is original to them. This image is compared by the level3 merchant authenticator for percentage of equivalence. Based on the result from the authenticator, the buyers can decide to buy the item or not. Here a high percentage of image similarity give buyers a higher sense authenticity of the item, boost their confidence on the originality and quality. Whereas a low percentage of equivalence is the reverse, as customers automatically decides that the advertised item is fake.

Furthermore, the seller authenticator is a bit similar to the customers or buyers authentication. Here the sellers of items upload the image of the item they have to sell. Once submitted, the level three seller authenticator checks the percentage of similarity between the sellers uploaded item image and same item image stored in the authenticator database. A higher percentage is an

outright acceptance for onward display to prospective buyers, while a low percentage of equivalence is an outright rejection. In between the high and low, item may be accepted but with high risk that will scare customers from buying. Therefore such item may suffer low patronage on the shop.

Figure 3: Flowchart of propose system

3.2 Image processing method

The proposed system employs canny edge detection algorithm for image segmentation and identification of manufacturers embedded trademark in other to further pixel wise comparison (Saini et al., 2013). This action is performed on both seller advertised product image and prospective customers image.

Canny edge detection algorithm developed over 33years ago (Canny, 1986) is still considered a more effective edge detection algorithm used by academics and industry today, due to its efficiency in edge search optimization problem solution.

A typical canny edge detection algorithm consist of the following steps

Step 1: Remove the noise from the image using a a tow dimensional Gaussian approximation technique on both x and y axis, due to the excessive resource utilization in two dimensional Gaussian computation

Step 2 : Obtain the changes in the x and y dimensions (gradient), because every changes in both dimension indicates an edge presence

Step 3: Exclude all lower gradient values, to identify the real edges in the image. Due to the fact that edge occurs in areas where there is high gradient value.

Step4: Mark out edge pixels through a process known as threshold (high and low threshold values) using the “hysteresis” technique, sub-division as followed:

- When the value of a pixel is more than the threshold highest value, then the pixel is selected as an edge
- When the value of a pixel is more than threshold low value, but if it is next to the pixel of an edge, Then, the pixel is selected as an edge.
- When the value of a pixel is more than threshold low value and it is not next to the pixel of an edge, Then, the pixel not selected as an edge.

After the all image edges has been properly segmented, to identify the product manufacturer embedded trademark for authentication, a pixel wise comparison between user uploaded images and intended item image comparison is carried out and the result is expressed in percentage. The degree of resemblance is shown by the higher the percentage, the more authentic the item.

The figure 4 exhibits the execution flow of the image processing engine for the proposed system.

Figure 4: Image processing engine for the proposed system

4.0 Results

The proposed model introduces significant advantage of the use of image processing as an authentication mechanism for enhancing the suitability of high value items on electronic commerce. Amongst which includes;

- i. reduces cost for inspection to zero percentage on both sellers and buyers
- ii. Improve the presence and patronage of high value to costly items on electronic commerce
- iii. Real-time authentication at no extra time or days needed, as in the case of manual inspection and verification.
- iv. Boost customers confidence on electronic commerce transactions on highly valued and costly items
- v. Verifies merchants items integrity

5.0 Discussion

High value cost items like jewelries, gold, silver, diamond and other precious ornaments receive the red flag from buyers due to the cost and value of the items, lack of trust and the lack of facility to inspect, verify and/or authenticate the item before purchase is made. A novel approach towards boosting consumer confidence in high valued cost items in electronic commerce business platform through online verification and inspection was proposed. In this proposed model, customers are given the opportunity to upload a live image from their home and

compare it with the image of the item they intend to purchase. Notwithstanding, image comparism is influence by many factors amongst which includes;

- i. Camera technology and quality: the quality of the camera used by either customer or seller goes a long way determining the quality of the image pixels which in turn hamper the percentage of similarity between the images of items uploaded by either customer or seller and those stored in the merchant system. For instance a poor percentage may be obtained in the case of users with poor camera, thereby forcing them to believe the item is fake, while other customers with high quality camera and images obtains significantly higher percentage of similarity. Hence false result will be very high, and research in containing this problem will be highly appreciated in future especially in areas of multiple image processing, such feature extraction before comparism.
- ii. Image background: Where the image is taken and what surrounds the image also impairs the percentages of similarity. Hence fixture extraction research in combination with comparism operation will be most needed to deal decisively with this challenge, in order to ensure accurate result from the system operation.

6.0 Conclusion

Electronic commerce is a great platform for any business but ensuring safety and trust between seller and buyer during transaction is very important and that was the research goal. The proposed system uses image processing (watermark) that is embedded in an electronic commerce platform to ensure trust and safety during transaction as items are compared and verified by the system which totally eliminates physical inspections by the buyer.

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